

Effects of Farmers Field Schools on Improvement Farming Practices for Increasing Crops Yield, North Kordofan, Sudan

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ABSTRACT:

Farmer Field Schools aim to improve farmers' knowledge and skills to achieve Good Agricultural Practices (GAPs). This study was conducted due to a shortage in farmers' knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards certain agricultural practices in the study area. The purpose of this paper is to identify the effects of Farmer Field Schools as a training approach to improve farmers' agricultural practices and increase crop production in the study area. A purposive sampling technique was used, and 120 respondents were selected. Data collection tools included a reconnaissance survey, questionnaires, group discussions, and direct observations. Secondary data were gathered from scientific papers, books, relevant authenticated websites, and reports from relevant institutions. The data were analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22) with a focus on descriptive analysis and Chi-square tests. The findings illustrate that 85.0% of the participants acquired knowledge regarding the latest agricultural technologies, 61.7% of the respondents perceived the FFSs as effective training tools for providing knowledge and skills, and 96.7% stated that they became experts in managing their farms. Additionally, 100% of the respondents expressed interest in observing the changes that occur due to the agricultural practices acquired. Their practices improved, and crop production increased after participating in the Farmer Field School programs to 10-15 *Jawal* and more compared to 5 *Jawal* before. The results of the Chi-square test showed significant associations among the tested variables. The results highlight the effects of Farmer Field Schools as a training approach to improve farmers' agricultural practices. Recommendations include improving the extension system and providing direction for future agricultural stability.

Keywords: Field school, Improvement, Practices, Sudan, Yield.

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INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), challenging targets have been set for agriculture, food security, and the conservation of natural resources [21]. The World Extension Forum has emphasized a people-centric, bottom-up approach to extension work for over three to four decades [1]. Farmer Field Schools (FFSs) are a popular education and extension approach globally ('Final impact evaluation of FFS implementation in the smallholder tea sector', 2016) and were developed in the 1980s by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) in Indonesia to promote integrated pest management (IPM) [2]. In Africa, FFSs were introduced as an extension method in 2006 by the Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA). Motivated by good results from a

pilot project with 24 FFSs in 2008, KTDA introduced the FFS program to all 54 KTDA factory companies between 2009 and 2016 [3]. Proper management of information sets a foundation for the delivery of efficient and effective extension services by providing accurate information to those who need it, when they need it. Other important issues include increasing farmer participation in sustainable agricultural development programs and agricultural extension services. Decentralizing activities and facilitating local group applications are the most important approaches for agricultural extension in the future [4].

The term FFSs comes from the Indonesian expression 'Sekolah Lapangan', meaning field school. It is a group-based learning process where farmers carry out experimental learning activities to help them understand the ecology of their rice fields [5]. FFSs are a group-based adult learning approach that teaches farmers how to experiment and solve problems independently [4]. Farmer Field Schools are an applied instructional method for group learning; they are not classrooms in regular schools but rather open-air learning areas at the farm level. They aim to stimulate innovation at the local level to achieve agricultural development [22].

Extension services improve farmers' knowledge base through means such as demonstrations, model plots, specific training, and group meetings. Exposure to such activities is intended to increase farmers' ability to optimize the use of their resources and ultimately increase crop yields. An ideal extension service provides a feedback mechanism from farmers to research centers [6].

The educational material of Farmers field schools (FFSs) are current field problems and farmers represent their students where the process of teaching and learning for agricultural technologies. It is a small group (25-30) farmer that meet under the shadow of a tree or any suitable place in the middle of farmers field, sacrificial fields and field experiments in participation and easy to reach the meeting is held weekly for 2-3 h [7]. Most FFS projects aim to provide training in skills to improve agricultural production, recently reorient FFS to include empowerment objectives such as reducing gender inequality, targeting minority groups, community development, and strengthening producer groups, it has become effective mechanism in this respect [8]. FFS helps to increase farmer knowledge, and studies in several Asian countries demonstrated that FFS could be effective in reducing the excessive use of chemical pesticides [2], cash crops, food crops, chickens or goats and special topics on nutrition, HIV/AIDS, water sanitation and marketing [9], and may vary according to the crop and country. The main problem in the area of the study occurred due to shortage in farmers' knowledge and skills towards some agricultural practices in the study area. This paper aim to find out the effects of farmers field schools training on improving the agricultural production of crops in the study area. Specifically, (1) to determine the training techniques followed for increasing knowledge and what knowledge and skills acquired, (2) to explore the perceptions of farmers towards farmer field school as training tools, and (3) to test significance association between some socio-economic characteristics and agricultural practices delivered to respondents.

METHODOLOGY

Study Site

North Kordofan State is located in the central part of Sudan, is one of three states forming greater Kordofan. Arid and semi-arid zones that cover the largest part of this state the area is estimated to be about 239,000 km² [10]. It lies between latitudes 12° 10' and 16° 30'N, longitudes 27° and 32° 35'E is divided into eight localities. Sheikan locality lies between longitude 29-35 East and latitude 12-25, 13-45 North equatorial. About 0.8 million fedan are fertile in the locality, Suitable for agriculture activities and the average land utilized annually is about 480 thousand fed [11]. The locality is characterized by a Wood land Savanna Zone (Semiarid Zone), rains range between 250-450 mm annually. It Starts in May and continues through October, with high precipitation in July and August. In recent years only the period between July and September is considered as the effective growing period. April and June are the month that show very high temperature, the maximum degree in Elobeid town during 30 years ranged between 37.8 and 39.8°C. The highest degree was recorded in 1972 and it reached 44.4°C. The temperature level during January and February shows a very low degree, the average range between 13.5 and 15.5°C [12]. The soils can generally be divided into two groups A group of coarse-textured soils (sand soil and kaizens soils) and group of soft-

textured soils (cordodoa soils and some scattered clay pockets) Gum Arabic production and forestry products contribute significantly to household income. Animal raised are mainly sheep, camels and goats [13,20] (Figure 1).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The study population consisted of all 120 participants in FFSs conducted in the area during the period 2012-2022. Purposive sampling technique was used and elected all farmers participated in four schools (120) (Table 1).

Data Collection

The study depends on primary and secondary sources from data collection. Primary data were collected from structured questioner, group discussion, key informants in the villages, and direct observation, while the secondary data were collected from scientific papers, books, relevant authenticated website, and report from relevant institutions.

Figure 1. Study Area

Table 1. Total Number of Framers Participated in FFSs in Area

Village name	FFSs	Number of participants	Gender		Selected sample	%
			Male	Female		
Abu am saadain	A	30	19	11	30	100
	B	25	15	10	25	
El karra	C	30	20	10	30	
	D	35	22	13	35	
Total		120	76	44	120	

Data Analysis

The collected data were coded and fed to computer and statistical package for several sciences was used (SPSS), focus on descriptive statistical (frequencies and percentages) and Chi-square Test to find associations among the variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of Descriptive Analysis

The results in Table 2 show that 87% of the respondents conducted frequent exchange visits, which enhanced their understanding of agricultural aspects. Table 3 shows that 99.2% of the respondents

shared all the information they learned from the field school with farmers who did not participate in the field school. This is evidence of the generalization of benefits among them.

Table 2. Distribution of the Respondents According to Visits Exchange

Exchange visits	Frequency	%
Always	47	39.2
Sometimes	40	33.3
Seldom	27	22.5
None	6	5.0
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 3. Distribution of the Respondents According to Farmer's Communication Techniques

Informal communication	Frequency	%
Always	119	99.2
Sometimes	1	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 4. Distribution of Participants According to the Use of Pesticides Before Participated in FFS

Reducing pesticide use	Frequency	%
Always use	24	20.0
Sometimes use	19	15.8
Seldom use	72	60.0
not use	5	4.2
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 5. Distribution of Participants According to the Knowledge Regards to Modern Agricultural Techniques

Level of knowledge	Frequency	%
High	102	85.0
Medium	18	15.0
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 6. Distribution of Participants According to the Knowledge Acquired Regarding to Types and Behavior of Insect

Information about different pests	Frequency	%
High	106	88.3
Medium	14	11.7
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

The results in Table 4 show that respondents mainly depend on their endogenous knowledge when using pesticides. 60.0% of the participants rarely use agricultural pesticides and prefer to use mechanical techniques. This indicates that farmers in the area rely on local practices for land cleaning and weed control. Table 5 shows that 85.0% of the participants acquired knowledge regarding the latest agricultural technologies through dialogue and active discussion in the FFS. This

reflects their interest in agricultural technologies and suggests the possibility of adopting modern technologies in their fields.

Table 6 shows that 88.3% of the participants were able to identify pests, their types, and the damage they cause. All this knowledge and skills were acquired through learning by doing in the FFS, which helps them maintain the health of their farms. Table 7 shows that 58.3% of the participants can diagnose diseases that attack plants. This result aligns with [14], who stated that methods like FFSs are effective in creating awareness among many farmers in a short time.

Table 8 shows that 75.0% of the participants have a high level of knowledge to identify insects as natural enemies. This result indicates the respondents' interest in accessing further training regarding biological control. Table 9 shows that 48.3% of the participants have poor knowledge of weed control methods. This is evidence of a lack of information on this issue and underscores the need for consideration. This result agrees with [15], who reported that subject matter specialists are poorly trained and not linking research with training functions.

Table 7. Distribution of Participants According to Knowledge and Skills Acquired to Diagnosis Plant Diseases

Ability to diagnosis	Frequency	%
High	70	58.3
Medium	49	40.8
Weak	1	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 8. Distribution of Participants According to Knowledge and Skills Acquired to Diagnosis Natural Enemies

Level of diagnosis	Frequency	%
High	90	75.0
Medium	29	24.2
Weak	1	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 9. Distribution of Participants According to Skills Acquired Ability to Diagnosis Weed Control Methods

Level of diagnosis	Frequency	%
High	51	42.5
Medium	11	9.2
Weak	58	48.3
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 10. Distribution of the Participants According to Knowledge and Skills Acquired to Determining the Percentage of Germination and Seed Quality

Ability determination	Frequency	%
High	93	77.5
Medium	25	20.8
Weak	2	1.7
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 10 shows that 77.5% of the participants acquired knowledge and skills to determine the level of germination and seed quality. This result confirms that the respondents have greatly benefited

from the FFSs. Table 11 shows that 96.7% of the participants have a high level of knowledge that helps them determine the optimal plant density for crop growth on the farm. This indicates the effectiveness of the training methods presented to them in the Farmer Field School. This result is supported by [16], who reported that extension methods enhance learning by doing and improve farmers' skills to become experts in their farms.

Table 11. Distribution of Participants According to Their Skills Acquired to Determining Plant Density

Level of ability	Frequency	%
High	116	96.7
Medium	4	3.3
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 12. Distribution of Participants According to Improve Their Skills in Agricultural Operations

Improving agricultural operations	Frequency	%
High	117	97.5
Medium	3	2.5
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 13. Distribution of Participants in Decision-Making Process

Decision-making skills	Frequency	%
High	119	99.2
Medium	1	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 14. Distribution of Participants According to Skills Acquired for Solving Problem Encountered

Problem-solving skills	Frequency	%
High	119	99.2
Medium	1	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 14 shows that 99.2% of the participants have high problem-solving skills that help them throughout the production season, making farmers feel confident and safe. [17] referred to agricultural extension as making farmers experts and innovators. Table 15 shows that 99.2% of the participants strongly agreed that there is an improvement in productivity and production after completing FFSs, and the acquired skills enhance problem-solving, as evidenced by their Mukhamas production.

Table 16 shows that 96.7% of the participants strongly agreed that they have become experts in managing their farms after receiving training and exercises offered by the Farmers Field School. This is in line with [17], who referred to agricultural extension as making farmers experts and innovators.

Table 17 shows that 61.7% of the respondents perceived the FFSs as good training tools for providing knowledge and skills and changing attitudes. This result agrees with [18], who reported that the ability and willingness of these farmers to adopt improved production practices may have been affected by the introduction of agricultural reforms stemming from FFSs.

Table 15. Distribution of Participant According to Their Perception in Crop Yield After Solving Production Problems

Increased production	Frequency	%
I strongly agree	119	99.2
Agree	1	0.8
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 17. Distribution of Participants According to Their Evaluation FFSS

Evaluation of the field school	Frequency	%
Excellent	46	38.3
Good	74	61.7
Total	120	100

Source: Filed Survey (2023).

Table 18. Chi-Square for Significant Association Between the Educational Level and Contribution in Dialogue in School

Variable		Contribution in dialogue in school		Total	Sig.
		Always	Sometimes		
Education	Illiterate	22	7	29	0.01*
	Khalwa	9	4	13	
	Primary	54	2	56	
	Secondary	15	3	18	
	Higher education	4	0	4	
Total		104	16	120	

Note: $P \leq 0.05$ = Significant, indicating by Chi-square test; $X^2= 11.8$.

Source: Study Area (2023).

Table 19. Chi-Square for Significant Differences Between the Gender and Knowledge Acquired Concerning Control Methods

Variable		Knowledge acquired concerning control methods			Total	Sig.
		High	Medium	Weak		
Gender	Male	36	3	37	76	0.03*
	Female	15	8	21		
Total		51	11	58	120	

Note: $P \leq 0.05$ = Significant, indicating by Chi-square test; $X^2= 7.32$.

Source: Study Area (2023).

Table 20. Chi-Square for Significant Differences Between Land Ownership and Knowledge Concerning Methods of Agricultural Practices

Variable		Knowledge concerning methods of agricultural practices			Total	Sig.
		High	Medium	Weak		
Land ownership	Owned	43	6	40	89	0.05*
	Rent	8	5	18		
Total		51	11	58	120	

Note: $P \leq 0.05$ = Significant, indicating by Chi-square test; $X^2= 5.8$.

Source: Study area (2023).

Results of Chi-Square Test

To achieve the study objective 'to test the significance of the association between some socio-economic characteristics and agricultural practices delivered to respondents', the Chi-square results in Table 18 indicate a significant association between educational level and participation in dialogues at school. This suggests that education increases the opportunity to participate in technical package application activities. The Chi-square results in Table 19 show a significant relationship between gender and knowledge acquired concerning control methods (classifying insects as natural enemies on the farm). This result is consistent with [19], who reported that the dissemination of productive information plays a crucial role in the farming society. The Chi-square results in Table 20 reveal a significant association between land ownership and knowledge of methods for agricultural practices, particularly integrated pest management (classifying insects and plants as natural enemies on the farm). Farmers typically care about their land and have the right to make decisions regarding any experiments related to pest control or inspection.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Knowledge and skills are permanent features acquired through learning. The results of the descriptive analysis indicate that there is knowledge and skills acquired due to participation in FFS, which has led to improved agricultural practices among farmers and increased crop production in the study area. Additionally, there is a positive trend and perception towards FFS conducted in the area. The results of the Chi-square test showed a significant association between some socio-economic characteristics and agricultural practices delivered to respondents. The study recommends that more attention should be given to institutions working in agriculture in Sudan in general and North Kordofan in particular, as well as to extension cadres. Furthermore, targeted communities should be selected carefully to ensure collaboration and the provision of services.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHORS

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. 1 is encourage and approved idea, verified the analytical methods, investigated and supervised the finding this work. 2 presented idea, developed the theory, and conducted filed work. Both authors discussed and approved the final manuscript.

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